

Appendix A: Selection of SC candidates for spectroscopic observations

We will not make a strict distinction between globular and open clusters, since the difference in late-type galaxies is mostly a question of mass.

For the period up to 2010, lists of SCs in NGC 7793 have been provided by Olsen et al. (2004), Mora et al. (2009), and subsequently by Krumholz et al. (2015). Young clusters (Larsen 1999, 2004) and stellar associations Pietrzyński et al. (2005) have also been inventoried in this galaxy. Up to 2010, the globular cluster (GC) systems of the Sculptor Group galaxies have been the subject of several spectroscopic studies, although the early samples remained rather limited. Beasley & Sharples (2000) analyzed 1 GC in NGC 55 and 14 in NGC 253, while Mora et al. (2008) studied 8 GCs in NGC 45. In addition, Olsen et al. (2004) carried out a more extensive survey and reported the discovery of 19 new GCs in NGC 55, NGC 247, NGC 253, and NGC 300, thereby bringing the total number of spectroscopically confirmed GCs in the Sculptor Group to 36. Interestingly, they did not confirm any genuine GCs in NGC 7793. More recently, Nantais et al. (2008) confirmed two additional GCs in NGC 253 and 12 in NGC 300 (9 of which have radial velocities consistent with membership in the galaxy).

We have analyzed the available in 2010 lists of SCs in NGC 7793 selected on the basis of their shape and photometry. For SCs in the outer regions of the galaxy, we selected candidates from the list of Olsen et al. (2004), based on their proximity to the tracks of SSP and/or galaxy models (Kotulla et al. 2009) in a $(C - T_1)$ vs. $(M - T_1)$ diagram. Unfortunately, only two objects (Olsen-GC 43 and 44) were visible on HST/ACS images; the first is a galaxy and the second a star. For the others, we relied only on their photometry for selection. We eliminated all candidates with $(C - T_1) > 1.8$, as they are beyond the model tracks. We also eliminated candidates with $(C - T_1) < 1.8$ that were too far from the model tracks. This leaves a total of 49 SCs for the outer regions.

We have also analyzed HST/ACS images of NGC 7793 available on the Hubble Legacy Archive site (<http://hla.stsci.edu/>) using SExtractor (Bertin & Arnouts 1996), and selected those objects that had the appearance of clusters and colors $(I - V) > 0.0$, eliminating stars with diffraction spikes and galaxies with a smooth appearance. We then plotted our SCs in a color-color diagram, together with SSP and E-galaxy GALEV models, which nicely bracket our SCs. The images of the candidate clusters of Mora et al. (2009), Larsen (1999, 2004), and Pietrzyński et al. (2005) were also inspected. Unfortunately, the coordinates of the four SCs of Mora et al. (2009) are not available, nor is their HST/ACS photometry. We checked all the objects in their HST/WFPC photometry and did not retain any. The total number of the selected SCs is 36, with m_B ranging between 17.2 and 22.1, corresponding to M_B of -10.9 and -5.9 , respectively. On the other hand, EL nebulae were selected by visual inspection of the HST/ACS images of NGC 7793. We could identify a list of 11 EL nebulae.

Figures A.1, A.2, and A.3 show HST images of the target objects.

Appendix B: Properties of the emission-line compact nebulae

The extinction-corrected emission-line fluxes and equivalent widths for the compact EL nebulae (see Sect. 4.1) were measured as described in that section. For each spectrum, the line

fluxes were normalized to $H\beta = 100$ and corrected for reddening.

The full table of extinction-corrected line fluxes $F(\lambda)$ and equivalent widths (EW) for the EL nebulae (Slits 8, 13, 16, 25, and 26) is provided as a machine-readable supplementary file (Table B.1), available as dataset material together with this paper.

Appendix C: Absorption-line spectra of SCs in NGC 7793

In this section we present the absorption-line spectra of SCs in NGC 7793 and the corresponding model fitting results, used to determine their radial velocities, ages, and metallicities (see Sect. 4.2 for details).

References

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Table B.1. Extinction-corrected line fluxes $F(\lambda)$ ($F(\text{H}\beta) = 100$) and equivalent widths (EW, \AA).

Line (λ \AA)	Slit 8	Slit 13	Slit 16	Slit 25	Slit 26
[O II] 3727.00	—	—	—	138.0 ± 6.0 169.0 ± 3.0	—
H12 3750.15	—	—	—	3.0 ± 0.0 4.2 ± 0.3	—
H11 3770.63	—	—	—	3.2 ± 0.0 4.3 ± 0.3	—
H10 3797.90	—	—	—	5.2 ± 0.0 7.1 ± 0.3	—
H9 3835.39	—	—	6.9 ± 1.0 3.1 ± 0.2	6.5 ± 0.4 7.7 ± 0.3	—
[Ne III] 3868.76	—	—	9.9 ± 1.1 5.1 ± 0.5	17.8 ± 1.0 20.4 ± 0.5	—
He I+H8 3889.00	—	—	22.8 ± 1.7 11.0 ± 2.1	19.0 ± 1.0 25.1 ± 0.8	20.0 ± 2.0 13.6 ± 0.9
[Ne III]+H7 3967.50	—	—	20.1 ± 1.07 11.1 ± 2.1	19.4 ± 2.0 28.8 ± 2.0	20.0 ± 2.0 17.0 ± 1.0
H δ 4101.74	—	—	29.0 ± 2.0 18.2 ± 0.7	25.0 ± 2.0 34.4 ± 0.9	22.0 ± 2.0 21.0 ± 1.0
H γ 4340.47	48.0 ± 2.0 190.0 ± 4.0	47.0 ± 12.0 3.1 ± 0.5	50.0 ± 3.0 39.0 ± 1.0	48.0 ± 3.0 72.0 ± 2.0	48.0 ± 3.0 61.0 ± 2.0
[O III] 4363.21	3.2 ± 0.2 11.5 ± 1.0	—	—	—	—
He I 4387.93	—	—	0.4 ± 0.1 0.3 ± 0.1	—	—
He I 4471.48	4.1 ± 0.2 15.1 ± 0.6	—	4.3 ± 0.3 3.7 ± 0.2	4.7 ± 0.3 7.7 ± 0.4	2.5 ± 0.7 3.0 ± 1.0
H β 4861.33	100 ± 3 436.0 ± 9.0	100 ± 10 13.0 ± 1.0	100 ± 5 112.0 ± 4.0	100 ± 5 183.0 ± 6.0	100 ± 4 238.0 ± 6.0
[O III] 4958.92	162.0 ± 7.0 547.6 ± 11.9	31.0 ± 6.0 4.6 ± 0.7	70.7 ± 4.9 81.4 ± 2.2	135.1 ± 5.5 270.5 ± 6.6	51.1 ± 3.0 108.9 ± 2.5
[O III] 5006.85	485.0 ± 13.0 1070.5 ± 17.5	61.3 ± 7.2 9.5 ± 0.9	206 ± 8 231.8 ± 5.4	372.7 ± 13.8 523.3 ± 9.3	159.8 ± 5.2 226.8 ± 4.2
[Cl III] 5517.71	—	—	0.4 ± 0.2 0.8 ± 0.3	0.6 ± 0.2 1.7 ± 0.4	—
[N II] 5754.64	—	—	—	0.3 ± 0.1 0.7 ± 0.4	—
He I 5875.60	11.7 ± 0.4 80.0 ± 2.2	4.2 ± 2.7 1.5 ± 0.9	12.8 ± 0.6 24.6 ± 0.8	16.0 ± 0.7 44.5 ± 1.3	8.7 ± 0.8 37.8 ± 3.0
[O I] 6300.30	1.7 ± 0.1 14.1 ± 1.0	3.3 ± 1.7 1.5 ± 0.7	0.7 ± 0.2 1.5 ± 0.4	—	1.2 ± 0.5 6.2 ± 2.5
[S III] 6312.10	1.9 ± 0.1 15.9 ± 1.1	—	0.8 ± 0.2 1.9 ± 0.4	—	0.8 ± 0.7 4.4 ± 3.4
[O I] 6363.80	0.5 ± 0.1 3.9 ± 0.8	—	—	—	—
[N II] 6548.10	5.1 ± 0.2 35.4 ± 1.3	33.3 ± 3.7 20.9 ± 1.6	8.4 ± 0.5 20.8 ± 0.8	—	11.7 ± 0.8 54.5 ± 3.3
H α 6562.80	288.3 ± 10.0 1089.4 ± 25.6	290.0 ± 23.4 161.0 ± 4.8	282.3 ± 12.6 384.9 ± 9.0	—	276.0 ± 11.2 585.0 ± 15.3
[N II] 6583.40	15.6 ± 0.6 122.4 ± 3.3	97.0 ± 8.4 61.6 ± 2.6	24.5 ± 1.6 62.3 ± 3.4	—	37.4 ± 1.9 174.7 ± 6.7
He I 6678.10	3.3 ± 0.2 28.4 ± 1.2	—	—	—	—
[S II] 6716.40	12.3 ± 0.5 106.5 ± 3.5	—	—	—	—
[S II] 6730.80	9.1 ± 0.4 80.1 ± 2.4	—	—	—	—

Fig. A.1. HST postage stamps of the observed objects (see Table 2). The size of the field of view is $\sim 10 \times 10$ arcsec.

Fig. A.2. Same as in Fig. A.1 but for the objects Slit 17 – Slit 28.

Fig. A.3. Same as in Fig. A.1 but for the objects Slit 29 and Slit 30.

Fig. C.1. Absorption-line spectra of SCs in NGC 7793 (black) in comparison with a composite model (green). Bottom: difference between the observed and the model spectra (see Sect. 4.2 for details).

Fig. C.2. Same as in Fig. C.1 but for the SCs: Slit 14 – Slit 20.

Fig. C.3. Same as in Fig. C.1 but for the SCs: Slit 21 – Slit 32.